

1 **HER2 is activated in circulating tumor cells in human prostate cancer.**

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6 Cancer cells separate from the primary tumor and enter the vasculature and disseminate to a foreign site.
7 We previously described genes expressed in the circulating tumor cells in humans with metastatic breast
8 cancer. Here we measured total transcription in circulating tumor cells from humans with metastatic
9 prostate cancer to discover genes activated in the circulating tumor cell in humans with a second type of
10 cancer, prostate cancer. Surprisingly, the epidermal growth factor receptor gene *ERBB2* was activated in
11 circulating tumor cells in men with prostate cancer. The data demonstrate that HER2 plays a role in
12 hormone receptor positive cancer across tissue and that in multiple tumor types HER2+ plays an
13 important role in the life cycle: in metastasis or dissemination.
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